

Blockchain-Based Smart Contract System for Secure Vehicle Registration and Onwernship Transfer

Vishakha Patil¹, Mihir Patil², Pallavi Patil³, Ms. Tejashree Pangare⁴

^{1,2,3,4}Dept. Computer Engineering Pillai HOC College of Engineering and Technology (Mumbai University) Rasayani, India

Abstract- AutoChain the word itself gives the idea about our project, Auto stand for Automobile and Chain stands for Blockchain. the ownership transfer and vehicle registration was managed traditionally that is with the help of the paper work. These conventional methods often suffer from the inefficient behaviour such as time complexity, lack of transparency, susceptibility which may lead to fraud, tampering of data and untrusting parties of human errors. Smart contract is a platform which does not include an intermediary between two parties or individuals. As we know that purchasing or transferring vehicle is a pretty risky job which cannot be taken for granted. Traditionally all the vehicle registration work or transfer work was done on paper work. And keeping securely that hard copies might lead to false copies or misplaced. So to avoid all these stuffs we invented our system.

Keywords: Smart contract, transfer, Blockchain, vehicle, registration, vehicle registration, secure transactions, records.

I. INTRODUCTION

Autochain is build with two separate words. Extending them Auto means Automobile and chain refers to Blockchain. So the word itself gives us the idea about our project which is build with the help of smart contract. Smart contract is a platform which does not include an intermediary between two parties or individuals. As we know that purchasing or transferring vehicle is a pretty risky job which cannot be taken for granted. Traditionally all the vehicle registration work or transfer work was done on paper work. And keeping securely that hard copies might lead to false copies or misplaced. So to avoid all these stuffs we invented our system.

As our system has large dataset which can carry upto thousands of paper work into a single chip. This becomes easier for the seller as well as buyer to handle the details of the vehicle securely. All the details of the vehicle starting from the date it is purchased till the date it is in process all the details are secured stored into the data base. This system will include vehicle details such as history of the car brought from which seller, purchase date and all internal hard core system with its features. With the use of smart contract, the intermediary between

the seller and buyer will get reduce so no worries about extra cost and untrusty work.

II. BACKGROUND

Before such process came into process, the ownership transfer and vehicle registration was managed traditionally that is with the help of the paper work. These conventional methods often suffer from the inefficient behaviour such as time complexity, lack of transparency, susceptibility which may lead to fraud, tampering of data and untrusting parties of human errors. This new software system is based on a platform that will store the details of the vehicle as many years and any one can view the details if needed. As it has smart contract no need for cost estimation or paper work. All records are securely stored and risk of misplacing or misusing them is very low. This will ensure less time complex system with large dataset and real-time verification.

III. MOTIVATION

Beside traditional performing transferring and ownership process our project provides a comprehensive analysis of the verification techniques with the help of smart contract. Smart contract is a system which eliminates the middle man between two individual parties. Provides a secure

and one to one communication between the seller and buyer. This shows the growing importance in the blockchain based systems as they can be used in various fields. As we know smart contract are the self-executing programs which are stored on the blockchain as it automatically enforces the agreements between the two individual parties.

As we know that in traditional systems errors, bugs or vulnerabilities can lead to severe financial losses and security breaches which can make verification most critical step before the deployment of the systems. We have studied many tools among which some are Mythril, Oyente and Securify. They have the ability to detect the issues like re-entrancy attacks or overflows of the interger, they still suffer from the limitations such as incomplete coverage, false positive and lack of scalability. These provided steps ensure that the verification of the current step landscape is still maturing. In the absence of standardized framework they often make it difficult to complete contract ensuring with correctness.

IV. FUNDAMENTAL CONCEPTS

Autochain Nexus covers the fundamental concepts that works out in the foundation of the proposed system. The project is integrated with the blockchain technology which is formed with the help of smart contract and cryptographic mechanisms.

This ensure secure, transparent and tamper- proof vehicle registration and ownership transfer. Another important term in blockchain is Cryptography. Cryptography is used to ensure data privacy and security through encryption techniques and safeguarding the sensitive vehicle and other information of the owner. This system will include vehicle details such as history of the car brought from which seller, purchase date and all internal hard core system with its features. With the use of smart contract, the intermediary between the seller and buyer will get reduce so no worries about extra cost and untrusty work.

**Literature review of the research papers:
Skill Verification Using Blockchain Technology
(2024)**

This paper proposes a blockchain-based system to verify skills and certificates using smart contracts. It focuses on eliminating fake credentials and improving verification efficiency.

Advantages:Certificates become tamper-proof and instantly verifiable. Reduces fraud and manual verification effort.

Limitations:Scalability issues as records increase. Requires blockchain knowledge and infrastructure.

Christidis & Devetsikiotis (2016) – Blockchains and Smart Contracts for IoT

This paper explains how smart contracts can automate IoT transactions securely and transparently

Advantages:Enables automation through smart contracts. Improves real-time data integrity.

Limitations: Requires complex implementation. Platform dependency.

A Review of smart contract Verification Method (2025)

This paper reviews different tools and techniques used to verify smart contracts for security risks. It highlights how bugs can cause serious financial losses.

Advantages: Helps detect vulnerabilities in smart contracts. Improves trust in blockchain applications.

Limitations: Verification tools are complex. Cannot detect all security issues accurately.

Zheng et al. (2018) – Blockchain Challenges and Technical Issues

This paper identifies major technical challenges in blockchain systems such as scalability, privacy, and energy consumption.

Advantages: Provides deep technical insights. Useful for system improvement planning.

Limitations: Mostly theoretical. Lacks practical solutions.

Vehicle Registration – New York DMV (2018)

This document explains the traditional vehicle registration and transfer procedure in New York.

Advantages:Shows real-world implementation. Helps understand existing system structure.

Limitations: Process is slow and manual. No automation or blockchain integration.

Kshetri (2018) – Blockchain’s Role in Enhancing Cybersecurity

This paper explains how blockchain technology improves cybersecurity by ensuring data integrity, decentralization, and fraud prevention.

Advantages: Enhances trust and transparency. Reduces data tampering risks.

Limitations: Regulatory challenges. High implementation costs.

V. EXISTING SYSTEMS

The existing system of the Autochain Nexus is primarily focused on vehicle registration and ownership transfer. Traditionally all the vehicle registration work or transfer work was done on paper work. And keeping securely that hard copies might lead to false copies or misplaced. So to avoid all these stuffs we invented our system. And not only this but the process included multiple intermediaries. Such as Regional Transport Offices (RTOs), agents and banks. This led to more and more time-consuming process and also costly which is prone to human error and false prediction of the documents. So to stop this there was a strong need for decentralized, secured and automated solution like blockchain.

As blockchain is a decentralized computation analysis and information sharing platform that enables multiple authoritative domains to work on a single platform. It also makes the process more efficient and builds trust in vehicle registration and ownership transfer. This new software system is based on a platform that will store the details of the vehicle as many years and any one can view the details if needed. As it has smart contract, no need for cost estimation or paper work. All records are securely stored and the risk of misplacing or misusing them is very low. This will ensure a less time complex system with large dataset and real-time verification.

All the details of the vehicle starting from the date it is purchased till the date it is in process, all the details are secured and stored into the database. This system

will include vehicle details such as history of the car brought from which seller, purchase date and all internal hard core system with its features. With the use of smart contract, the intermediary between the seller and buyer will get reduced so no worries about extra cost and untrustworthy work.

Ensuring to deliver the scope of this project, this system is to design and implement a blockchain-based smart contract system which ensures secure, transparent, and efficient vehicle registration and ownership transfer between the vehicle owner and seller. The system focuses on eliminating the dependency on centralized authorities by introducing a decentralized ledger where all stakeholders — including vehicle owners, buyers, transport departments, and insurance agencies — can securely access and verify records. The project automates the key operations of vehicle registration, verification, and ownership transfer using smart contracts, thereby reducing paperwork and manual intervention.

This system can be extended to include integration with insurance companies, emission testing centers, and financial institutions for loan verification and renewal services. In the long term, the project aims to create a tamper-proof, scalable, and trustless framework that can be adopted nationwide to enhance transparency, reduce fraud, and simplify administrative processes in the transportation sector.

Fig 1: Integrated Representation of Existing Systems

VI. PROBLEM STATEMENT

As the traditional systems are centralized they can lead to tampering of the data and forgery of data. And the manual verification and multiple intermediaries lead to delays, they provide high costs and human errors and may ask for some cost. After so many study there is no further delays in verification of ownership history that may cause fraudulent transaction. So AutoChain is a blockchain based decentralized system that can ensure security, transparency and immutability in transfer of vehicle.

VII. PROPOSED SYSTEM

The proposed system utilizes blockchain technology and smart contracts to automate and secure the process of vehicle registration and ownership transfer. The methodology involves several integrated modules that ensure transparency, security, and reliability throughout the transaction process.

Step 1: User Interaction

The process begins when the car owner interacts with the interactive web application. This web-based platform allows users to register their vehicle details, initiate ownership transfer requests, and view transaction history.

Step 2: Authentication through MetaMask

Before proceeding, the user is authenticated via MetaMask, a crypto wallet extension that enables blockchain-based transactions. MetaMask verifies the user's identity and securely connects their blockchain account to the web application.

Step 3: User Signature Verification

The user sign interaction ensures that all transactions are digitally signed by the registered user. This digital signature provides non- repudiation and ensures that the transaction is authorized by the legitimate owner.

Step 4: API Communication

The web application communicates with the blockchain network using an API (Application Programming Interface). The API retrieves user requests, processes them, and executes smart contracts accordingly.

Step 5: Smart Contract Execution

The smart contract is automatically triggered once the request is validated. It defines the rules and conditions for vehicle registration or ownership transfer and executes them without requiring manual intervention.

Step 6: Blockchain Storage

Upon successful execution of the smart contract, the transaction data is stored permanently in the blockchain. This ensures that all records are immutable, transparent, and verifiable by authorized entities.

Step 7: Vehicle Data Registration

Finally, all validated information, including vehicle details and ownership status, is securely stored in the vehicle data registration database. This decentralized record prevents data manipulation and enables efficient verification for future reference.

Fig 2: Proposed System Flow

VIII. METHODOLOGY

As the system consist of many stages in accordance with the smart contract. The first stage is the

Requirement analysis phase. This phase is used to identify the need of the stakeholders which include the vehicle owners, vehicle buyers and government agencies. And based on these requirement of the system like security, transparency and automation there is a suitable platform called Blockchain. That platform is the Ethereum and Hyperledger. It is selected for the use.

Then comes the smart contract, they are used as they are designed and developed to automated the key process. This next process include the vehicle registration, payment handling, ownership transfer and also document verification.

The next step in the process is the Architecture. This architecture is crated by integrating the decentralized application (dApp). This dApp is created with a user interface, backend services, and the blockchain interaction which provides the base for the good system. Finally the solution is deployed and monitored, as it is enabling real-time tracking of vehicle transaction on the blockchain.

IX. CONCLUSION

The system is designed to automated the vehicle registration and ownership transfer between the owner and the seller. This system is build with the use of smart contract which will eliminate the intermediaries. This will result into transparent, secure and efficient vehicle registration and transfer. As we are using smart contract we are reducing paper work, ensuring faster approval rather than days for clarification.

The records are stored on an immutable blockchain ledger. Which will claim all the fake ownership and illegal resale. This this decentralized nature of the system build with trust among buyers, sellers, and government authorities by maintaining accountability and transparency in every transaction to ensure good framework for the seller. Beside the vehicle registration, in every transaction it provide good framework for the seller with trust.

X. RESULT DISCUSSION

Fig 3: Home Screen

Fig 4: User Interface

Fig 5: Vehicle Data

Fig 6 : New Vehicle Registration

Fig 7 : Ownership Transfer

Fig 8 : Blockchain

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